

Reply to: Rectifying misinformation on the climate intervention potential of ocean afforestation

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This file contains our responses to Smetacek et al.'s first and second versions of their *Matters Arising* Comment they wrote as a Response to our paper: "Testing the climate intervention potential of ocean afforestation using the Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt" (<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-22837-2>). Especially the first Comment they drafted made some substantially different arguments than the version that got finally published. We include our replies to their previous versions here for full transparency.

Our reply to the first version of Smetacek'et al's Matters Arising Comment.

Main

We thank Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹ for commenting on our study. When addressing our analyses², their critique mainly focuses on our data selection and some of our conclusions which do not favour ocean afforestation. We will first respond to these specific aspects. Next, we explain that their contrasting conclusions are the result of arguments being based on seaweed growth potentials while our assessment is based on the concept of “additionality”. We then elaborate on why an assessment that considers additionality is the more pertinent.

Data selection

Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez suggest that the estimated range of CO₂ removal (CDR) reduction from 20-100% is “based on the highest numbers dealt with in the text hence amount to misrepresentation”¹. Their comment is incorrect. The 20% reduction in the CDR potential of ocean afforestation was estimated by propagating the lower bounds in the literature while a 100% reduction is based on propagation of the upper bounds. These balanced results, from best- to worst-case scenario, were carefully and consistently articulated throughout the abstract and the main text.

One specific example where biased data selection was incorrectly implied by Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez refers to the calcification feedback: They suggest that our highest value for CaCO₃ wet weight biomass percentage (21.4%) was “based on an old decrepit specimen collected on a Bermuda beach”¹. First, this *Sargassum* sample was collected in the Sargasso Sea near Bermuda, not on a beach³. Second, the value was simply the highest of 13 reported for *Sargassum*³. We used the lowest value (4.3%)³ to present exactly the same calculation for the best-case estimate.

We question whether Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez provide a balanced knowledge base to underpin their arguments in favour of ocean afforestation. This becomes evident throughout their text when they portray the promise of ocean afforestation, such as their extrapolation of exponential *Sargassum* growth from 1 tonne to 10 gigatonnes biomass within a year or their advocacy for “biodiversity and climate security”¹. More critically, however, this lack of balance is also reflected in their own data selection. For example, they argue for ocean afforestation by stating: “*Sargassum* has almost tenfold higher carbon to elemental ratios (C:N and C:P) compared to phytoplankton^{4,5}”. The relevant paper by Lapointe cited here (the other is a self-citation referring to the same Lapointe paper) shows that C:N in *Sargassum natans* is 2.5-10-fold higher than phytoplankton (C:N=6.6), with 10-fold being the upper bound (C:P 2-10-fold with 10-fold again being the upper bound)⁴. Our analysis of differences in C:N and C:P between *Sargassum* and phytoplankton is based on the full range C:N and C:P (Figs. 2B and S1 in Bach et al., 2021), provided by a more recent dataset by Lapointe et al.⁶. Thus it considers the best and worst cases, and not only the best case as by Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹.

The need for a scientific assessment of ocean afforestation

Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez argue that a critical assessment gives undue publicity to evidence against ocean afforestation¹. They state that equal attention to the “pros and cons” of ocean

afforestation would “lend traction to [the] attempt to denigrate seaweed farming [...]”¹. Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez thereby allude to the so-called false balance problem in climate change communication where the scant evidence against climate change has often received comparable media coverage as the overwhelming evidence for climate change⁷. By drawing this comparison, they imply that the potential of ocean afforestation is already validated by a multi-decadal IPCC-like knowledge base and that its upscaling is merely “an engineering problem”¹. We disagree with their misleading allusion and stress the many biogeochemical and ecological unknowns and complexities around ocean afforestation⁸⁻¹³. The knowledge base is not fit to provide a scientific assessment of ocean afforestation as concluded by high-level reports calling for massive research and development needs before up-scaling of any marine CDR method can be considered, including ocean afforestation^{14,15}. This conclusion, opposite to Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹, is also drawn by the other responses to our *Sargassum* paper^{16,17}.

Additionality needs to be considered for ocean afforestation assessment

Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez question whether naturally occurring pelagic *Sargassum* is an appropriate analogue for ocean afforestation¹. Instead, they describe the emergence of highly productive seaweed aquaculture as a better analogy. Along these lines, they praise the “phenomenal growth rate” of *Sargassum* thereby arguing that *Sargassum* is well suited for CDR¹. These thoughts indicate that Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez evaluate the CDR potential of ocean afforestation primarily by how much carbon can be fixed per unit time. This is fundamentally different to our “additionality-based approach”, which evaluates ocean afforestation based on how much additional carbon seaweeds (in our case *Sargassum*) would sequester than the baseline phytoplankton ecosystem they replace².

CDR via ocean afforestation is essentially an attempt to make the existing biological carbon pump more efficient. The biological carbon pump is mainly driven by plankton communities and its strength in the subtropical Atlantic is limited by the availability of nutrients¹⁸. Nutrient limitation will continue to limit the biological carbon pump under hypothetical ocean afforestation, with a fraction of the available nutrients no longer fuelling phytoplankton carbon sequestration, but seaweed carbon sequestration instead. Embracing this biogeochemical constraint, it immediately becomes apparent that afforested seaweeds need to achieve higher carbon sequestration per limiting resource (mostly N in the subtropical Atlantic¹⁹) than the phytoplankton system it took the nutrients from. Thus, it is neither the “phenomenal growth rate” of *Sargassum*¹ nor the potential for growth in the seaweed sector¹ that matters. The most pertinent variable is the difference in carbon-to-nutrient stoichiometry between phytoplankton and seaweeds². Since pelagic *Sargassum* has about 2 to 13.5-fold higher C:N (0.7 to 8-fold for C:P) than phytoplankton⁶, we estimated on average a net-gain in carbon sequestration by the replacement of phytoplankton with seaweeds (i.e. ocean afforestation)². Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez mention the C:N ratio in their response, but do not draw robust conclusions from it¹.

Within the concept of additionality, it is also short-sighted to propose artificial upwelling as a way to enhance *Sargassum* growth¹. This is for two reasons. First, artificially upwelled waters can be upwelled naturally elsewhere and fuel productivity of phytoplankton communities some time in the future. Thus, artificial upwelling would shift the problem of nutrient reallocation in space and time (this argument has already been made in our original paper²). Second, fertilising *Sargassum* would drastically reduce its carbon-to-nutrient stoichiometry²⁰ and therefore reduce its potential advantage in carbon fixation efficiency relative to phytoplankton. Thus, counterintuitively, faster growth of

Sargassum enabled through artificial upwelling would reduce the CDR potential of ocean afforestation within this stoichiometric framework that is based on additionality.

Conclusion

Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez disagree with our assessment of ocean afforestation¹ but provide no evidence that would alter the conclusions in our original paper. Our analysis provides best- and worst-case scenarios based on data available in the peer-reviewed literature. In contrast to Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez, we conclude that real-world efficiency of ocean afforestation has not yet been assessed sufficiently to justify its upscaling² (neither has its environmental implications⁹). Rigorous application of the concept of additionality is essential for such an assessment, and will also help to avoid replication of the poor carbon accounting evident from terrestrial afforestation, where additionality is insufficiently considered²¹.

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Our reply to the second version of Smetacek'et al's Matters Arising Comment.

Main

We thank Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹ for commenting on our study. Here, we provide our Reply to the second (heavily modified) version of their Comment, noting that their first version made some substantially different arguments. Since responding to their first version provided potentially useful clarifications, we publish our reply to the first in the supplementary material. We encourage Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez to do the same so that the science community benefits from reading the full exchange of arguments.

In the revised version of their appeal, Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez argue for the large potential of ocean afforestation while providing hypothetical solutions for its anticipated limitations. For example: The reduction of the Ocean Afforestation potential through the nutrient re-allocation problem^{2,3}? Can be fixed when extracting and recycling nutrients from seaweed biomass somehow¹. Or: Deep ocean deoxygenation following the deposition of seaweed on the seafloor⁴? Can be avoided by baling the biomass prior to sinking to limit respiration¹. It is easy to come up with these hypothetical solutions, but much harder to pass them through a reality check.

The absence of such a reality check was what motivated us to utilize the “Great Atlantic Sargassum Belt (GASB)” as a natural analogue for the scientific assessment of Ocean Afforestation. Smetacek's and Fernandez-Mendez's main criticism in their revised Comment is that the GASB is not a suitable analogue for Ocean Afforestation¹. They provide mainly two arguments. First, the GASB is only a megatonne-scale phenomenon and hence fixes much too little CO₂ to provide relevant insights for gigatonne-scale Ocean Afforestation¹. Second, Sargassum grows too slowly in the GASB to be comparable to necessarily fast-growing seaweeds envisioned for Ocean Afforestation¹.

Their¹ scale argument is not reasonable. Ocean Afforestation would not go from zero to gigatonnes in one big step but this process would occur gradually with a certain growth rate⁵, as we can observe in sectors where seaweed is grown for products⁶. Thus, Ocean Afforestation would need to eventually pass the megatonne-scale of the GASB. If Ocean Afforestation could not provide verifiable CO₂ removal at the megatonne-scale, then there would be little incentive to move forward to the gigatonne scale. As such, assessing ocean afforestation on the megatonne-scale of the GASB is relevant and useful for a potential real-world implementation of Ocean Afforestation.

Their dismissal of the GASB due to limited *Sargassum* growth rates¹ is based on the argument that Ocean Afforestation depends on artificial upwelling to enable gigatonne-scale seaweed biomass production. Indeed, already pioneering field trials in the 1970s found that the benthic seaweed *Macrocystis* does not grow in the open ocean unless fertilized with both nutrients sourced from depth and iron fertilizer sourced from land⁷. As such, we agree that gigatonne-scale seaweed biomass production may depend on concomitant artificial upwelling^{1,4,5,8} and ocean iron fertilization⁹. However, and in contrast to Smetacek's and Fernandez-Mendez's conclusion¹, lessons learnt from the GASB analysis on Ocean Afforestation would still apply as will be argued in the following two paragraphs.

The nutrient re-allocation problem discussed in our current and other studies^{2-4,8} assumes: Nutrients that are used to fuel seaweed CO₂ fixation are no longer available for phytoplankton. Thus, the enhancement of an anthropogenic CO₂ sink (Ocean Afforestation), would reduce a natural one (phytoplankton). As such, the net gain in CO₂ fixation depends on how much more carbon the seaweeds can fix with the available amount of limiting nutrients than the phytoplankton were able to fix before their replacement^{3,10}. This can be estimated from the difference in carbon-to-nitrogen stoichiometry between seaweeds and phytoplankton, which is usually in favour of seaweeds¹⁰. However, in contrast to implications made by Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹, evidence suggests that nutrient-replete conditions (as they would be induced through artificial upwelling) lower carbon-to-nutrient ratios in seaweed^{10,11} while potentially increasing phytoplankton carbon-to-nutrient ratios¹². Thus, artificial upwelling could induce conditions that collectively reduce the efficiency of Ocean Afforestation.

Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹ argue that the nutrient re-allocation problem would not apply if nutrients were sourced via artificial upwelling from depth because the deep-ocean nutrient inventory is huge. This thought is conceptually misleading because what matters is not the pool size but what would happen to the artificially upwelled nutrients in the absence of artificial upwelling. For example, if nutrients were artificially upwelled from 530 m depth in the (sub)tropical North Atlantic, then they are available to fuel new CO₂ fixation instantaneously. In the absence of such artificial upwelling these nutrients would have been upwelled naturally within the next 50 years¹³ and fuel phytoplankton productivity in the future. The deep ocean is not a homogenous reservoir but stratified itself and exchange between layers is limited¹³. It cannot simply be assumed that nutrients taken from some ocean depth through artificial upwelling would be fully or partially replaced through the remaining deep ocean nutrient pool. Thus, the nutrient re-allocation problem remains and must be integrated over timescales of which the deep ocean naturally exchanges nutrients with the surface ocean. This will make accounting for the nutrient re-allocation problem even more difficult.

Artificial upwelling is also associated with other severe impacts on various climate-relevant processes¹⁴⁻¹⁶, which are not mentioned by Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez¹. Artificial upwelling at a specific location must lead to downwelling elsewhere, with unknown implications for CO₂ fixation in the downwelled water. Artificial upwelling of colder water cools the surface but increases heat retention in the Earth system¹⁶. Artificial upwelling brings respired CO₂ to the surface, which needs to be overcompensated through subsequent CO₂ fixation by seaweeds to not be lost to the atmosphere^{15,16}. Thus, artificial upwelling is by no means an easy fix for the critical nutrient re-allocation problem but comes at a huge cost of making the assessment of the net climatic impact of Ocean Afforestation considerably harder.

To conclude: We note that Smetacek and Fernandez-Mendez provide a supportive narrative for Ocean Afforestation¹. While our study revealed that Ocean Afforestation could potentially lead to additional CO₂ sequestration in the oceans, we cautioned that this biotic CO₂ removal approach is highly complex and unpredictable³. Determining if and how much additional CO₂ is sequestered by Ocean Afforestation will be extremely challenging³ and will become even greater when fuelling the method with artificial upwelling. Robust carbon accounting, also known as “monitoring, reporting, and verification”, is a key constraint for the implementation of any CO₂ removal method¹⁷. Thus, implementation of ocean afforestation is handicapped to a great extent by its relatively large inherent complexity. We stand firm with our original conclusion³ that other, abiotic, CO₂ removal methods with less inherent complexity have more potential to deliver verifiable CO₂ removal in the near-term.

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